

Dynamics of Employee Engagement

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Employee engagement is the most fundamental integral concept of an organization which defines and directs the progression of a system. The nature of relationship both qualitative and Quantitative between the decision makers and the executors and the coordinated sharing of their responsibilities and mutual concerns are the prime factors incorporated in the progressive growth of an organization. The performance, interest, dedication and ownership of the assigned duty are the salient characteristics of an "Engaged Employee" which speak volumes of the real health of an organization. In Compendium, a good employee engagement system is expected to outperform a bad employee engagement system despite the other elements being in favour of the latter.

Employee engagement being a modern concept replaced the archaic paradigm of looking at employee as insignificant factor. Born in late nineties the concept of Employee Engagement became a key feature in the twenty first century as productivity and profit ran in consonance with employee satisfaction and performance. Hence employee engagement played a pivotal role in the management and performance of human resources.

In most of the top leading companies it has been observed that senior managers and decision makers have not only inculcated the feelings of trust responsibility, ownership, dedicated commitment of their employees but also have provided reasonable perks, , benefits, aid and work-life incentives to them. Thus, to turn efficient but disengaged employee into a positive company culture rather than hiring, experimenting and laying off, is the prime concern of an organizational setup with a long term goals.

To empower, to motivate and align its employees with objectives of the system speak volumes of its performance, thereby making the human asset a key component of any organizational structure.

Understanding the dynamics of Employee Engagement :

1. Organizations are incorporating new HR practices to address critical issues on job performance in order to cultivate positive work culture in employees. The new practice takes care of organizational citizenship behaviour, task commitment, effective mutual communication, investment in employees' needs and demands etcetera.

2. The American workforce report 2017 by Gallup brings out some revealing inferences. The report clearly mentions that companies with higher performance growth view employee engagement as a business imperative, hence spend significant amount on improving employee relationship. Thus a "Culture of engagement" is key to HR policies.

3. Employee engagement is seen in three organizational roles - HR, leadership and employee. Several researched literatures offer methodologies of programs and initiatives an HR can execute to improve employee relation. A mélange of all three is mandatory to manifest the smooth functioning of the system. It means engagement is not merely reflected in expensive programs and one time motivational event - on the contrary, it intervenes, influences, provides and promotes. It convinces the employee and inculcates in them the feeling of ownership and thereby assuring a prolonged commitment towards the organization.

4. The high levels of employee engagement translates into retention a talent, faster customer loyalty and improve organizational performance and Stakeholder Value. (Lockwood, 2007) The effective employee engagements drive increases productivity, profits and customer satisfaction for the organization. (Harter, Schmidt & Hayes 2002 : Siddhanta & Roy , 2012), It also paves the way to make employees happier, more satisfied and more fulfilled and want to remain with the organization (Adejoh and Adejoh , 2013),

Employee Engagement in Indian Context :

Contextually, the need of the application of this concept is highly felt in India. The town of the new leader in global economy skill is in dire need to revamp its relation and understanding towards employee engagement. From the concept of golden goose that lay golden eggs - hence forcing a disengaged attitude of strangulating the employees with *low bucks - high performance benchmarks* to the practice of *personalized work - life balance attitude* - a paradigm shift is the need of the hour. Employee engagement could lead to high benchmark growth with vital job creation in Asian countries.(Gallup , 2013) like India.

It has been opined by many experts that employee engagement practice is high in double - digit growth companies which are exceeding average industry revenue growth. For a developing country like India with good economic growth contour the organizations could increase their competitive efficiency with effective human asset policies and contribute towards holistic growth of economy (Ellis & Sorensen 2007)

Deducing from here, is the concept that organizational citizenship behavior has emerged advocating that productivity and growth of an organization are predominantly decided by the employee's ability and commitment. It is believed that agile organizations are the outcome of engaged employees. Several valued studies on employee engagement in Indian context have offered suggestions with regard to long term stability, health and reputation of an organization. Many questionnaire based surveys conducted on organizations have reported employee disengagement being one of the factors for impeding the productivity.

Movers of Employee Engagement :

Employees committed to their duty perform better and this must be identified as major driver of engagement. To raise the engagement levels of the employees the organization must involve them to decision making process and give credence to their views. They must be treated as the real stakeholders of the organization. In words of Robinson, Perryman and Hayday Organization's concern for employees' health and wellbeing, are the vital necessities that drive the engagement.

Most of the researches advocate that non financial incentives too impact positively employee engagement if employees find meaning at work. Once their primary need is taken care of, they start adding value to their services. The prime driver to their efficiency and productivity is not money alone. Their desire to feed their views and opinions upwards remains a predominating factor in order to align them with the objectives and goals of the organization. Almost sixty percent (60%) of the employees seek opportunities for advancement in their profession (Blessing White, 2006). Opportunity to voice the decision and address of employees' well-being are identified as prime elements for engagement (Towers Perrin Talent Report, 2003).

The personal attributes play a key role in employee engagement (Townsend, Wilkinson, and Burges, 2014). An employee having skills, knowledge, temperament, attitudes and personality must be supported by affective HR practices, physical and social setting, and leadership in the organization to yield maximum from an employee (Vance, 2006). The employee engagement is intimately allied to the organizational practices. The employees working in a friendly and amiable environment feel more engaged (Clifton, 2008). Organizations, if, can align efforts with strategy, empower the employees, build coordinated teams, enable people to develop, and give recognition will reflect healthy growth.

Economy plays an influential role in fixing employees attitude towards the degree and level of his skill and ability investment. A strong economy leads to higher job satisfaction. It is seen that a better understanding of employee attitude results in effective management of employee well-being, making well-informed HRM decisions, and managing organizations effectively (Rich, Lepine and Crawford, 2010).

Inferences:

1. The employee engagement directly influences the health growth of any organization. The need is to connect with the employees, prepare interface with their individual goal with organizational goal, incorporate their presence as stakeholders and align their skills with the road map of growth.
2. Power of autonomy and participation in decision making should be encouraged.
3. Organizations must have transparent policies and train and mentor its employees in order to prepare future managers.
4. Grievance redressal mechanism must function strongly to make employees feel heard and justice be awarded to all.
5. Talent mobility, adoption of new culture and space for new methodologies should be practiced on regular basis.
6. A positive working environment where credence is paid to their views along with appreciation and recognition to their work becomes the culture of the organization.

CONCLUSION

In the face of growing economy like India a thorough research with subjective difficulties must be conducted so as to know the limitations of the organizations which despite an appreciable growth fail to execute new and effective employee engagement practices. The management of human asset is the key to productivity. The cognitive ability of the employee, his attitude of oneness with the road map of the organization and his personalized efforts in creating new benchmark of growth are to be studied carefully. A researched policy should be perceived, drafted and executed efficiently to honor the efforts and input of the employees.

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